

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DIALLO****FIRST NAME: GAELLE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 24 %

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Can a writer use both the US and UK English in the same paper?¹

- The writer must use only one version of English throughout the paper but use the original English version when citing a quotation.**
- Yes, the writer can use both at the same time.
- No, the writer can only choose one.
- Only when it can be justified.

Commented [KG1]: Footnote superscripts should be placed on the correct answers, not the questions. Kindly effect corrections across the entire paper. Also, shuffle the correct answers such that not only the first option is consistently the correct one.

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¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 86.

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2. What is the purpose of a qualitative proposal?²
- To present a clear argument that explains and justifies the logic of the study.**
 - It is chosen when the researcher is not presenting data.
 - It is used to support the methodology.
 - It is used to discuss literature reviews.
3. What are the necessary elements to build a strong proposal?³
- A clear problem statement, a purpose statement, a research question, a review of the relevant literature research, data collection and data analysis methods.**
 - The argument presented.
 - The research question and data collected.
 - No elements are necessary if the researcher presents valid data to support the hypothesis.
4. How does a scholar choose a research approach?⁴
- A qualitative proposal presents a clear argument that explains and justifies the logic of the study.**
 - Based on the researcher beliefs.
 - A brief overview of the argument.
 - Based only on the research.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 202.

³ [Jbid.](#), 202.

⁴ [Jbid.](#)

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5. What is the purpose of a qualitative proposal?⁵

- The qualitative research approach is chosen based on the research problem.**
- To discuss literature review.
- To discuss human factors in the research.
- It is used when quantitative research is not appropriate.

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6. What are the best sources of information?⁶

- Most recent primary and secondary sources.**
- Popular magazines.
- Commentary and opinion journals.
- Any publications holding the subject of the dissertation.

7. What type of literature review does a scholar need to support their research?⁷

- A Peer-review literature including journals and academic papers.**
- Any published article.
- Any article with an abstract.
- Articles found on selected databases discussing the topic of research.

8. Does the methodology always have to include genres or traditions?⁸

- The scholar must choose one or more genres to provide specific direction regarding the research design and research methods.**
- No, the scholar can omit the genres or tradition.

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⁵ [Ibid.](#), 135.

⁶ [Ibid.](#), 77.

⁷ [Ibid.](#), 353.

⁸ [Ibid.](#), 157.

- It depends on the topic of research.
- It depends on the methodology of data collection.

9. What is the role of a qualitative researcher?⁹

- The researcher endeavors to explain the meaning of the findings from the perspective of the research participants.**
- To provide their findings based on their beliefs.
- To provide data and let the reader interpret them.
- To describe findings and let the reader interpret them.

10. When is the abstract of a dissertation written?¹⁰

- The abstract is written after the dissertation is completed.**
- The abstract is written first.
- The abstract is written alongside the dissertation.
- Anytime during the process of data collection.

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⁹ [Jbid.](#), 151.

¹⁰ [Jbid.](#), 68.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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